

Insights to Inspire 2020 Blogs – Diversity, Equity & Inclusion

Blog 1 – Making a Commitment to Diversity & Inclusion

The purpose of the Careers in Clinical and Translational Research metric is to measure the success of CTSA Program hubs in training scientists who will stay engaged in the field specifically with regard to underrepresented persons (URP) and women. However, engagement is not the only factor for continued success. The value of science to society is the ability to both collect data and analyze problems from a variety of perspectives. That means diversity must be built into every aspect of the CTSA Program. Scientists with multiple perspectives are critical to the success of the Program. Furthermore, inclusion must be at the heart of the CTSA trainee programs. Only in this way can the CTSA Program improve the health of individuals and the public.

As a part of the Insights to Inspire 2020 series, the CLIC staff interviewed the program hubs that showed the most improvement in the Careers in Clinical and Translational Research metric, with a specific emphasis on diversity and inclusion. CLIC's goal in sharing the experience of the successful hubs is to turn their success into actionable intelligence for the entire Consortium.

Each hub identified for its success in the Careers in Clinical and Translational Research metric adopted a number of strategies or techniques in order to improve their TL1 or KL2 training programs. From the various interviews where diversity and inclusion was discussed, nearly every hub started with the same foundation for their success: "*commitment*". From there, hubs detailed additional activities to ensure they could deliver on that commitment.

Make diversity a stated goal

All the hubs interviewed for this article cited diversity and inclusion as core values and emphasized their importance throughout their research, education, and recruitment programs. Duke University's Clinical and Translational Science Institute specifically discussed how they made a commitment to increase their number of underrepresented scholars. Laura Svetkey, one of three co-Directors of the KL2 program at Duke, said the hub's most important strategy was making an explicit programmatic priority to achieve at least 50% of funded KL2 scholars from underrepresented racial and ethnic groups. "That's where it starts. Really having an intentional metric with institutional support to achieve it," Svetkey said.

Christy McKinney, Co-Director at the Institute of Translational Health Sciences (ITHS) at the University of Washington, is a graduate of the ITHS KL2 program herself, and engages with the KL2 scholars through teaching and mentoring during monthly small group sessions. ITHS Director of Evaluation Julie Elworth says having McKinney in that role serves as proof to female scholars and applicants that they too can succeed in clinical and translational science. "Having a woman who's been a scholar of the KL2 program and now be one of the program's co-lead helps people understand that the KL2 program is sincere about its commitment to women succeeding in the field," Elworth said.

Provide and promote the support systems

Beyond naming diversity as a goal, the highlighted hubs said implementing programs that specifically support both women and URPs with the unique challenges they face, such as lower quantity and quality of mentoring, implicit and explicit bias, competing responsibilities both at home and at work, were critical to success.

At the ITHS, that means being truly supportive of scholars, both men and women, who take time off for parental leave, meaning trainees and scholars are actively encouraged to take full advantage of programs that allow them to extend their tenure clock after leave.

The University of Colorado Denver CTSI had success in implementing a series of trainee-focused workshops based on topics specifically geared toward women and URPs. One such example is a workshop on how to respond to and mitigate microaggressions, the everyday verbal, nonverbal, or environmental slights, snubs, or insults these individuals often experience. They also provided workshops in crafting successful program applications and worked to connect URPs with faculty with similar identities to serve as coaches and advocates. Lisa Cicutto, Director of Translational Workforce Development Core and TL1 Director at Colorado, said trainees have found the workshops so helpful they are organizing additional programming for trainees and staff.

Several hubs stated the importance of what Rasheed Gbadegesin, Co-Director of the KL2 Program at Duke, described as a “community of past and present scholars” that serve as role models and peer mentors for their fellow female or URP scholars. The scholars also share their positive experiences, which helps build confidence in current scholars and promote hub programs.

Stay involved and supportive

In order to foster the kind of community where past scholars return to help their peers, ITHS Director of Evaluation Julie Elworth said it’s critical for scholars to feel the door is still open once they’ve completed the program. The hubs serve as a continuing resource throughout their career. “I think it’s important for the graduates of the KL2 program to know that they are part of this larger community and will be no matter what,” Elworth said. “Once they’re in the program, once they graduate, they remain in the ITHS family.”

Johns Hopkins University Institute for Clinical and Translational Research (ICTR) Director of TL1 Programming Mary Catherine Beach also said the ICTR pays attention to adversity as well as diversity. When recruiting, faculty/staff might notice hints from personal statements in an application, which reveals additional information from the applicant’s background they might otherwise leave unsaid. Statements that might get mentioned offhandedly – that the applicant grew up in poverty, had experienced serious illness or disability, or other challenges faced in overcoming educational barriers. While race or gender can inform a trainee’s perspective on clinical and translational research, so too can those types of lived experiences. Beach said that ICTR has adjusted their weighting system to minimize previous test scores and grades to not disadvantage applicants who faced education challenges.

Advocate

Many of the hubs interviewed also discussed how they intentionally made an effort to promote diversity of disciplines in their programs. In addition to recruiting applicants from traditional fields like medicine or biology, they also search for applicants with backgrounds in biomedical engineering, public health, applied health, and even the arts.

According to Kimberly Johnson, co-director of the Duke KL2, “it is important that the institution itself is committed to promoting diversity and inclusion. Our KL2 program has been able to capitalize on Duke’s commitment to both increasing the number of faculty from underrepresented racial and ethnic groups and providing resources to support their career development.”

In order to advance innovations and interventions in translational research, it is critical that the composition of the clinical and translational science workforce reflect the population it serves. By committing to diversity and inclusion, CTSA Program hubs can create the sense of community that ensures successful trainees will continue in and promote the field of clinical and translational science.

Blog 2 – Building Real Connections: Recruiting Future Clinical Researchers

For CTSA Program hubs, supporting and promoting the career development of their trainees and scholars can be a lengthy process. Before a hub can evaluate the success of their TL1 or KL2 educational training programs, before trainees or scholars can receive effective mentoring, every hub has to take the first step: recruiting researchers into the program.

As a part of the Insights to Inspire 2020 series, a number of hubs who demonstrated improvement in the Careers in Clinical and Translational Science Common Metric emphasized the importance of recruitment. These hubs found success through coordinated efforts focused on both cultivation and relationship building.

Program Champions

One of the most important ways for hubs to spread the word about training programs is by working within their home institution. The Michigan Institute for Clinical and Health Research at the University of Michigan (MICHHR) uses “champions” to help promote its TL1 program. Brenda Eakin, Program Director for Education and Mentoring at the MICHHR, says champions are university faculty with whom hub staff have developed collaborative relationships. For example, staff members may stay in contact with faculty members who have written letters of support for previous applicants. Once those relationships are established, the champions continue to connect potential trainees to MICHHR staff. MICHHR also schedules informational sessions to recruit pre-doctoral students to their programs including those in fields such as biomedical engineering and nursing. More recently the program has even begun reaching out to art disciplines across campus, as Eakin noted the arts can be helpful in engaging communities in research and bringing attention to clinical and translational science.

Similarly, the Indiana University CTSI works with “navigators” to provide outreach to trainees and promote translational research to a wide array of training programs across campuses, according to TL1 Principal Investigator Thomas Hurley. “As much as anything else I think it’s the penetration into all aspects of training that allows us to recruit a diverse pool to start with,” Hurley said.

Personal Interactions and Positive Experiences

Relationship development with faculty and staff at home institutions and at partner organizations can take time. Recently established hubs also need to provide both outreach and promotion as they establish partnerships. While a robust marketing strategy – including emails, newsletters and flyers – is important, the highlighted hubs agreed that face-to-face interactions are critical.

Kathlynn Wray, Program Coordinator for the Institute for Integration of Medicine and Science’s KL2 Program at the University of Texas Health Science Center at San Antonio, says it’s important for hub leaders to make the effort – to start those face-to-face interactions, to go to faculty meetings, to meet with department heads, to get the message out there. “It’s been on the shoulders of the Directors, the CTSA Leadership – the PIs – to talk to their colleagues about

it,” Wray said. “It was them literally talking to people and saying ‘Hey, we’ve got this program. Do you know what it is?’”

Another powerful tool for recruitment comes in the form of positive word of mouth from scholars or trainees who have completed the program. “I can tell them all the great things and benefits of the program but when they hear from another med student who has gone through the training how they’re using those skill sets and how they’re making them a better physician – that’s a lot more empowering than a flyer or promotional video,” Project Administrator Adisa Kalkan said of the TL1 program at the Clinical Research Training Center at Washington University School of Medicine in St. Louis.

Catarina Kiefe, Program Director of Mentored Career Development at UMass’s KL2 program, agreed with hub leaders that it is especially important to show women and underrepresented applicants there are people like them at a hub, and then to help them form connections and networks. Creating a supportive environment means it’s critical for institutions to place a priority on providing representation by hiring diverse candidates for faculty and leadership positions to serve as role models. “I think women speaking to women, especially about issues related to STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Math) and research, that’s really powerful,” Eakin said. “We make a real concerted effort so scholars can see themselves in the faculty mentors we have.”

The environment must also be welcoming, collaborative and ensure that recruits have what they need to flourish. Hub leaders say if recruits have a positive experience it increases the likelihood that program graduates will endorse and promote it by word of mouth. Nate Hafer, Director of Operations at the University of Massachusetts Center for Clinical and Translational Science, said people at the hub go out of their way to welcome new members of the KL2 training program, and to help them get connected to key resources so they can get started on the right foot. “I think that can be very important for people to get networked into the organization so they don’t feel like they’re wandering around,” Hafer said.

Building a Partnership

Similarly, Wray said it’s about truly being there for scholars and trainees, about trying to understand how the hub can help them and what they need to succeed instead of simply asking what are their deliverables and what can they do for the hub. “It becomes much more of a partnership,” Wray said. “They know they can come to us with any issue they’re having. They know they can come to us and we’re going to help them find a solution, not just pass them off.”

That support can take the form of insisting on institutional support for scholars and trainees. At San Antonio, KL2 Principal Investigator Joel Tsevat implemented a requirement that departments commit to a third year of support for scholars so that their research time is protected.

Another successful approach at the University of Kentucky Center for Clinical and Translational Science is providing support to applicants who aren’t selected on their first application to either the KL2 or TL1 programs, according to Director Philip Kern. Victoria King, Director of Career Development at Kentucky, said the hub often works to help refine rejected applications for

future rounds. “There’s been a number of times when a slot is open when we select someone but realize someone else is really strong, and we’ve gone to bat for these people to help get them protected time and other resources,” Kern said.

Once someone has become interested enough to consider applying, all the hubs interviewed stressed the importance and success of taking an individualized approach to working with that applicant. “When I tried to recruit people I tried to listen to them and make them understand I’m interested in them as a person and want to learn from them. It’s an issue of setting the right tone when trying to recruit somebody,” said Kiefe.

In addition to working with recruits themselves, several hubs noted their success in working with partner organizations outside their home institutions. The recruitment pool for Indiana University’s pre- and post-doctoral training programs includes scholars and trainees from the hub’s home institution as well as Purdue University and the University of Notre Dame. The MICHHR has also had success recruiting underrepresented persons by forming partnerships with the University of Puerto Rico and the University of Alabama.

All the advice shared by the highlighted hubs centered around two distinct but intertwined ideas: partnerships and connectedness. Building a successful recruiting strategy means building successful partnerships, which, for recruits, can best be done by making them feel like a part of the community and institution. It can take different forms, such as working with institutional faculty outside the hub, program graduates, or applicants themselves. But just as in clinical and translational science, collaboration is the key to success.

Blog 3 – Training Applications: Starting with a Strong Foundation

The purpose of the Careers in Clinical and Translational Research metric is to measure and develop strategic plans to enhance the ways hubs and the entire CTSA Program consortium are training and supporting the future workforce. This support is vital to helping trainees remain engaged in clinical and translational science. One of the earliest opportunities hubs have to support early-career trainees and scholars is when researchers first apply to the TL1 Clinical Research Training Awards and KL2 Mentored Clinical Research Scholar Awards programs.

For the 2020 Insights to Inspire Series, the Common Metrics Initiative identified hubs that demonstrated the most success in the careers metric for 2017-2018 in order to share the strategies and approaches that worked for them with the rest of the consortium. In particular, several hubs all had particular success in the application process. Following are strategies they found most impactful:

Start Early – with guidance and communication

Karen Freund, KL2 Program Director at Tufts University Clinical and Translational Science Institute (CTSI), said CTSI staff begin reaching out to interested scholars at least a year in advance of anticipated application deadlines. Hub staff start by meeting with potential applicants to lay out the entire timeline of the application process before reviewing all aspects of a successful application such as research aims, a training plan and a mentor team. Then, scholars are put in touch with the resources at the CTSI where they can get advice and an analysis of their plan. Scholars with an intended focus in specific areas like stakeholder engagement or data collection also meet with the hub team members who are focused on those topics. “We really feel like there is a potential to quickly provide applicants with a set of resources to provide the best application possible,” said Freund.

Victoria King, Director of Career Development at the University of Kentucky Center for Clinical and Translational Science (CCTS), said hub staff meet with new faculty and walk them through all the training and career development programs available to junior faculty in an effort to promote those programs to potential applicants. Similarly, Marc Chimowitz, Director of the KL2 Program at the Clinical and Translational Research Institute at the Medical University of South Carolina (MUSC), said the hub calls on program graduates and other successful researchers at the institution to both promote the program and to identify potential applicants.

Tufts also has two investigators who serve as navigators for applicants. The navigators introduce applicants to the hub and assist in making connections, such as finding a faculty mentor with expertise in specific laboratory skills, Freund said. King said the University of Kentucky hub has also had success with a hands-on approach to assisting applicants. Once enough potential applicants have submitted letters of intent, King and CCTS Associate Director Thomas Kelly convene a group of interested applicants to discuss the application process and the content of the training program. Then they meet with each potential applicant to explain specifically what they look for in an application. “We spend some time talking with the individuals and make sure they really understand what an application is and what’s important,” said King.

Raise the bar

Beginning in 2017, the Institute for the Integration of Medicine and Science at the University of Texas Health Science Center at San Antonio (IIMS) began requiring applicants to its KL2 program to complete a more rigorous letter of intent process and obtain a commitment of a third year of protected time from their respective departments. When first implemented, there was concern the higher threshold might scare applicants away, according to Joel Tsevat, Principal Investigator of the KL2 Program at the IIMS. However, just the opposite has happened. “If anything it has increased the number by making it more prestigious, something people are really proud of getting,” Tsevat said. Both Aubree Shay and Susanne Schmidt, the hub’s Co-Evaluators, said the increased requirements have resulted in attracting scholars who are truly committed to seeing the application process through to the end. The enhanced requirements – such as having first-author status on multiple publications – means applicants are usually further along in their careers, and ensures they are committed and likely to remain in the field of clinical and translational research. “Locally and nationally, programs are developing a cohort of researchers who are prepared for their next step when they finish their KL2,” Tsevat said. Janice Gabrilove, one of two career development leads at the Icahn School of Medicine at Mount Sinai Institutes for Translational Sciences, said the hub’s TL1 program elected to focus exclusively on URP applicants, while also requiring strict performance standards. “In the long run this approach was meant to serve as a pipeline to enhance recruitment and retention of talented URP candidates who will ultimately serve as role models at the faculty level.” She also indicated, “in the long run, our pipeline program will begin to address the deficiency of URP individuals at mid-career and senior faculty levels.”

Look beyond the paper application

At the Institute for Clinical and Translational Research at Johns Hopkins University (ICTR), Edgar Miller, *Deputy Director for Clinical Research Education, Training and Career Development*, said a *limited number of slots for its KL2 program meant the hub has, similar to the IIMS, placed a focus on applicants who might be further along in their careers and more likely to be successful. However, Miller said the hub also tries to be aware of whether or not they’re “cherry picking” by avoiding applicants who might have the energy and drive to succeed but might not look as good on paper.* To address that, the hub makes sure to place an emphasis on personal interviews with applicants -- especially regarding disadvantages faced by URPs that might not be apparent from applications. “How do you not only select for the most highly productive and connected and such that are going to be well on their way to success? How do you reach in and support people who are more disadvantaged when the outcome of success for the program is transitioning people successfully?” Miller said. Several of the hubs interviewed also emphasized the importance of continuing to work with applicants who are not initially accepted into training programs. Both the IIMS and ICTR said applicants who aren’t initially accepted receive feedback on their applications. This enables scholars to improve their future K applications.

One of the most important ways CTSA Program hubs can pave the way for interventions and innovations that improve the health of individuals and the public is by recruiting researchers who are committed to clinical and translational research. To accomplish that, hubs should

expect a commitment from scholars and trainees, and in return provide a strong foundation and a springboard, from which they can grow and further their careers.

Blog 4 – Mentorship: A Bridge to the Future

Effective mentorship is one of the most important contributors to a successful career in translational research. TL1 trainees and KL2 scholars benefit from the relationships and support that come from a well-planned mentoring program. During the 2020 Insights to Inspire series CTSA Program hubs that demonstrated success in improving the Careers in Clinical and Translational Research described the strategies they implemented, specifically focusing on mentoring and training.

Be a matchmaker

The first and perhaps most critical component of providing scholars or trainees with effective mentorship is to ensure program members are paired with mentors with compatible, complimentary skill sets and with whom they can build cooperative, beneficial relationships. David Brousseau, Director of the TL1 Program at the Clinical and Translational Science Institute of Southeast Wisconsin (CTSI) at the Medical College of Wisconsin (MCW) expressed that successful mentorship help recruits “build the bridge” to the rest of their careers. “The idea is that the best mentoring experience is what’s going to – one – allow them to be successful and – two – to want to continue in clinical and translational research,” Brousseau said. During the TL1 admission process, Brousseau explained that CTSI staff would solicit information about an applicant’s planned mentor to learn about their mentor track record. The CTSI also provides training for the mentors to allow trainees to have the best research experience.

Scholars entering the KL2 Program at the South Carolina Clinical and Translational Research (SCTR) Institute at the Medical University of South Carolina (MUSC) often come with their own mentors, according to Program Director Marc Chimowitz. MUSC prefers that already-assigned mentors have skills that align with the program criteria, including a strong record of funding, leadership experience, and a strong mentorship record. When appropriate, MUSC CTSI staff help trainees and scholars find a mentor within the program. MUSC also offers a mentor training symposium that is open to everyone on campus each year, as well as a four-week mentorship training course.

The Center for Clinical and Translational Science (CCTS) based at the University of Alabama at Birmingham has built a mentorship core that reflects the diversity of the university’s students and recruits. The program has been helpful in both attracting scholars and trainees and ensuring their success throughout the program, according to KL2 and TL1 Program Manager Jeanne Merchant. KL2 and TL1 Program Director Ken Saag says constructive mentor relationships create a symbiotic relationship that benefits the mentor as well as the mentee. And – with a mission to address the health disparities of the Deep South – that diversity helps the CCTS serve its mission. “It really does mean a lot to me that we’re able to select trainees that are from the same background as the people we’re trying to help with our research,” Merchant said.

Build a ladder

In order to maintain an effective diverse mentorship core for years to come, several hubs described the work they have done to build a pathway that helps trainees, scholars, and faculty become mentors. Nate Hafer, Director of Operations at the University of Massachusetts Center for Clinical and Translational Science, said the hub's "K Club" offers junior faculty a chance to hone their skills as mentors. It is a way of paying back the mentorships they benefited from when they were students and trainees.

Luisa DiPietro, Principal Investigator and Director of the KL2 program at the University of Illinois at Chicago (UIC) Center for Clinical and Translational Science, said their hub has been able to benefit from and build upon the diversity that she said is part of the fabric of UIC. "Often our job is linking our scholars to the right mentors and having a diverse group of mentors helps us do that," DiPietro said. After finding success early on, hub staff engaged former scholars from underrepresented groups and recruited them to serve as mentors. The hub's emphasis on team and mentor training also helps with mentor retention and success, so the mentorship core sustains itself.

Staff members at several hubs pointed to the importance of supporting research that can be uniquely relevant to women and underrepresented researchers. This support helps retain mentors, and helps recruit applicants. "We have funded scholars looking at impact of race on African American women and acculturation of Latinx women. I think when word gets around that you have a program willing to fund that kind of research program it's quite attractive," Brousseau said.

Supplement the mentoring

A positive relationship with a primary mentor is crucial for scholars and trainees, but many hubs offer additional programs to help program recruits develop their skills and further their careers. In addition to quarterly meetings with scholars and their mentors, Diana Lee-Chavarria, Education and Workforce Development Program Manager at MUSC, said the hub has implemented initiatives such as a "K to R Club" in which scholars from programs across the campus can learn about submitting grant applications, receive feedback from senior faculty and engage in peer-to-peer mentoring. Much of the support provided to faculty at the KL2 Program of the Mayo Clinic Center for Clinical and Translational Science (CCaTS), according to Dean for Clinical and Translational Science Sundeep Khosla, is focused on young women faculty and is meant to facilitate career development at an early stage across the institution. For example, the Leader Launch program – a collaboration between several of CCaTS' offices and an external consultancy that's designed to enhance women's leadership skills, builds confidence and provide support for them to complete research or entrepreneurial projects.

Chimowitz said one thing the KL2 program does *not* do is require excessive coursework from mentees. Instead, the program allows them to focus on their research. "Our job at the program is really to support them and give them the opportunity to conduct their research that will propel them to be successful as independent researchers," Lee-Chavarria said. Khosla said if protecting research time for program members means convincing institutional leadership to

allow for it, hubs should make the argument that such research is critical to the mission and reputation of hubs and the CTSA Program, and that divisions and departments should be evaluated on research as much as clinical output. “You have to support career development and research in order to come up with new therapies and to have the kind of reputation that patients are going to be willing to come to Rochester, Minnesota,” Khosla said.

Nearly every hub interviewed noted that the creation of a successful mentorship program that benefits both scholars and trainees comes down to one thing: dedication. “Training the next generation is like having kids. You’ve got to get them launched and provide unconditional support for their success and I think that’s the attitude most of us have,” said Saag.

Blog 5 – Follow up and Evaluation: Engagement for Positive Impact

The Careers in Clinical and Translational Research Metric is designed to measure and develop strategic management plans to enhance the ways CTSA program hubs train and support scientists to remain engaged in research. To measure and report the success of the metric, hubs conduct follow-up surveys to determine if scholars and trainees have remained in clinical research upon completion of the program. To that end, hubs must find ways to encourage graduates to respond to these follow-up surveys. Successful hubs have improved their KL2 and TL1 programs by being receptive to feedback and conducting ongoing evaluation.

A few of the CTSA Program hubs that achieved the most improvement in this metric between 2017 and 2018 were: Columbia University, Johns Hopkins University, Clinical and Translational Science Institute of Southeast Wisconsin (CTSI) at the Medical College of Wisconsin (MCW), South Carolina Clinical and Translational Research (SCTR) Institute at the Medical University of South Carolina (MUSC), Colorado Clinical and Translational Sciences Institute at University of Colorado | Anschutz Medical Campus, University of Kentucky Center for Clinical and Translational Science (CCTS) and University of Texas Health Science Center at San Antonio (UTHSCSA).

As a part of the Insights to Inspire 2020 series, these featured hubs were interviewed by CLIC staff to share their success at increasing survey response rates. These hubs achieved success through such efforts as emphasizing the need for program data, being open to and responding to scholar feedback, and staying in touch with scholars. CLIC's goal in sharing the experience of the successful hubs is to turn their practices into actionable strategies for the entire consortium.

Stay in touch, early and often

When it comes to overcoming the challenge of getting scholars to respond to program evaluations, it helps to engage in relationship-building and in early and ongoing communication about the importance of responding to evaluation surveys.

For MCW, that meant considerable one-to-one contact with scholars throughout the program. "During the scholars' orientation to the program, we reiterate as many times as we can how important it is for scholars to participate in the relevant surveys. This is important to the success of the program and in service of current and future scholars," said Ramez Rashid, Evaluation Director, CTSI of Southeast Wisconsin, MCW. "Throughout the program, we'll try to repeat the message ... we need the data so that we can develop and implement sustainable improvements."

MCW also focused on building relationships with scholars, which can be challenging given the short timeframe of the program. "It's a one- or a two-year program, and you have to really be pretty active in interacting with the students to get to know them, to get them to trust you," said Joe Barbieri, Associate Director of the TL1 Program. "We make the effort to interact with the students during the year to make sure that they are on track to find out what they are doing. And then as they graduate, we try to continue to have that relationship."

Johns Hopkins University emphasized expectations to its TL1 scholars, explaining that scholars have to stay in touch, so the university can track their career path and achievements. Communicating that expectation upfront seems to have worked, as a recent survey seeking information about their current employment and research sent to 69 alumni generated 68 responses.

Mary Catherine Beach, Director of Johns Hopkins' TL1 Predoctoral Clinical Research Training Program and Professor of Medicine, said, "We've been keeping in touch with people. We tell them all the time, this is what we are going to do for you. And, in turn, you always have to be in touch with us so that you can help us understand what you're doing with your life."

Another hub was more direct in how it communicates the importance of getting responses from individuals who finish its TL1 program. "It really is just letting them know when they start that we're going to be bugging them, that I'm going to be the biggest nag that they've probably ever had in their life," said Lisa Cicutto, Director for Translational Workforce Development and of the TL1 program at University of Colorado CTSI.

Staying in touch with scholars can also pay dividends after they graduate from the programs. Alumni can play significant roles as mentors to newly registered scholars and they can help promote the value of the TL1 and KL2 programs to potential scholars. The University of Kentucky CCTS program continues to hold in-person meetings with KL2 alumni, and the alumni remain actively engaged in program activities and in assisting faculty.

Be open and responsive to feedback

Featured hubs found success by being open to scholar feedback and to making programmatic changes based on that feedback.

At MUSC, program leaders actively supported their scholars, checking in with them regularly to see if they have concerns or if they are facing any issues. The goal was to help provide support without overburdening the scholars. Scholars participated in quarterly meetings with their mentor and with program leaders to discuss their progress and to provide feedback.

According to Rechelle Paranal, Evaluation Manager, leaders not only listened to feedback, they adjusted the program based on what they heard. "We used to do something at 5 p.m. and we moved it to 4 p.m. because people let us know that 5 p.m. is hard because you have to pick up kids then and there's too much going on at that time. So really listening to them and just making sure you're hearing what they say and what's going to help them get supported ... that's something that's really important."

Use formal evaluation tools

As most scientists recognize, quality research depends on having reliable data behind it. For hubs to evaluate their TL1 and KL2 programs, they must have good data. In addition to the informal modes of collecting feedback from scholars, featured hubs relied on formal evaluation tools to collect data as well.

At Columbia, an evaluation form — a combination of an individual development plan and an internal progress report — solicits information about which goals have been met, which goals are still in progress, the number of papers published, along with general feedback regarding what scholars think of the program. For program alumni, a survey is conducted to gauge whether the graduate is currently engaging in team science. The survey collects such information as current and past employment and leadership responsibilities, titles, and the types of research conducted since graduation.

UTHSCSA and MCW worked to begin collecting program data from the outset. UTHSCSA conducts individual KL2 scholar interviews with the evaluators rather than program staff to gauge effectiveness and solicit unbiased feedback, both at the mid-point and end of the program. Using the Clinical Research *Appraisal* Inventory (CRAI) tool, MCW conducts self-evaluations of scholars' skills upfront, and the CRAI is given again once the scholars complete the program. MCW program leaders then evaluate the delta and conduct a statistical analysis to determine if there was a significant improvement in skill levels according to various criteria. In addition to the CRAI evaluation tool, MCW also conducts a graduate tracking survey that follows the graduates over many years to gauge their efforts and their output in terms of grant applications, promotions and other outcomes throughout their career after graduating from the program.

The activities and experiences of these featured hubs demonstrate that soliciting and responding to feedback, and early and ongoing relationship building can assist in improving evaluation and follow-up efforts and overall programs. For some hubs, the “secret sauce” is having an open-door policy, from the beginning of the program through graduation, to make the scholar/alumni-program evaluator relationship a two-way street.

“I think it’s just our involvement with each of the scholars,” said Daichi Shimbo, Columbia’s KL2 Director and Associate Professor of Medicine. “We work with them frequently ... and have an open-door policy if any of the scholars want to talk about career development issues. And I think by emulating that kind of environment people are more likely to respond because you help them.”

The University of Rochester Center for Leading Innovation and Collaboration (CLIC) is the coordinating center for the Clinical and Translational Science Awards (CTSA) Program, funded by the National Center for Advancing Translational Sciences (NCATS) at the National Institutes of Health (NIH), Grant U24TR002260.